

1th. International Conference on Design in Civil Engineering,
Architecture and Urban Planning / 29 February 2024

Venue: Azerbaijan - Baku

Assessing the Effectiveness of Viscous Damper in Enhancing Steel Frame Performance Level

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of a viscous damper in reducing the dynamic responses of a building structure while enhancing its performance level per FEMA regulations. The research paid particular attention to the placement of the viscous damper in different openings in the building frame, and to achieve this, they designed a 6-story building frame nonlinearly in the Opensees software, considering the connection spring and equipped with a viscous damper. The viscous damper was placed in two different ways in the building frame to study its impact. The research used three classifications of earthquake acceleration to analyze the structure dynamics, which are classified based on the maximum acceleration of the ground to the maximum velocity of the ground ratio. The viscous damper's parameters were optimized using the meta-heuristic algorithm. The study's results show that the viscous damper, with optimal parameters, effectively reduces the story drift ratio, increasing the structure's performance level. Specifically, the viscous damper placed in the side openings of the building frame reduced the maximum story drift by 90%, while the one set in the middle spans reduced it by 70%.

Keywords: Viscous Damper, Story Drift Ratio, Meta-heuristic Algorithm, Nonlinear Dynamic Analysis, Performance Level

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1. Introduction

In the structure's design, there is a constant trend in the static analysis: the structure will have the main task of bearing static loads and transferring them to the ground. During the dynamic analysis of the structure, the lateral forces on the structure will cause vibration. There are different theories to deal with these vibrations in the structure. Some researchers believe that the strength and ductility of structural members will be sufficient to deal with these dynamic loads, and others believe that they should use control tools to face and reduce the dynamic response of the structure. The use of control tools will reduce the forces affecting the structure. We will have three general passive, semi-active, and active categories to control the structure based on the consumed energy. Passive control tools have been widely used in terms of performance and cost because their performance does not depend on the input forces. The viscous damper is a passive or semi-active control system used in buildings to reduce the dynamic response of the structure against the dynamic loads of wind or earthquake. These types of systems will work by dissipating energy through a viscous fluid. This liquid in the damper reduces the dynamic response of the structure by controlling and resisting the movement [1]. In the studies, a procedure for the optimal location of viscous damper (VD) installation in tall structures was carried out based on the highest energy loss of the damper system. The proposed method estimates the place where the dampers should show the most energy loss [2]. In the studies conducted, the researchers investigated the viscous damper parameters for a type of bridge with a small and medium span. In this study, they analyzed the sensitivity of the seismic response to the viscous damper parameters in small and medium-span bridges. The results showed that the viscous damper with optimal parameters improves the seismic performance of the bridge [3]. In recent years, a study has been conducted on the performance of the viscous damper system in controlling the dynamic response of asymmetric structures, and the results show that using viscous dampers will increase the damping of the structure and ultimately reduce the displacement of the asymmetric system. [4]. In their study, Allami Mehmandousti and Jalaefar [5] studied the performance of viscous dampers under seismic sequences. The results concluded that viscous dampers significantly reduce the seismic responses compared to the uncontrolled frame. Singh and Kumar Tiwary [6] investigated the performance of viscous dampers considering composite columns and using isolators in concrete building foundations. The results showed that the viscous damper performs well in reducing the dynamic response of the stories when the isolator is not used, but instead, it increases the base shear in the building. Presented for more efficiency. Kaleybar *et al.* [7] investigated the effects of the placement of the viscous damper on the middle frame of the structure. The results showed that using a viscous damper with optimal placement will increase the performance level of the structure. In the course of studies, the performance of the controlled structure using viscous dampers under the stimulation of near-field earthquakes has been investigated, and a parametric study has been proposed to propose the damping coefficient [8]. In the following studies, the performance of the viscous damper has been

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examined. From the results, it has been concluded that the viscous damper has a positive effect on reducing the dynamic response of the structure [9]. Fabrizio Scozzese *et al.* [10] studied the influence of the viscous damper's ultimate capacity on the structure's seismic reliability. A fluid viscous dampers (FVD) model accounted for the impact forces arising when the FVD reaches the end-stroke. The effect of damper failure on the fragility and seismic risk of the system was investigated by performing a multiple-stripe analysis and monitoring various global and local demand parameters.

Magar Patil *et al.* [11] presented their research on the seismic function of steel moment frames equipped with buckling restrained braces and fluid viscous dampers. They used seven modified acceleration time histories for incremental dynamic analysis and compared the energy dissipation of the two systems. Kang *et al.* [12] introduced an innovative damping system with a saw mechanism of FVDs. Braces are only exposed to tensile forces in this system, and the buckling problem was inconceivable. In research by Dilip *et al.* [13], fluid viscous dampers were used for the control of vibrations caused by seismic shocks. They experimentally investigated the behavior of FVDs under half sinusoidal shocks. They also developed a numerical analysis and mathematical formulation for the performance of FVDs under shocks and pulse loading. The effect of damper nonlinearity and complementary damping were studied as well.

The study highlights the importance of the location of viscous dampers in the construction of buildings. The performance of the system can be significantly impacted by the placement of the dampers, which can reduce the dynamic response of the structure. To evaluate this point, the study was conducted in two cases where the viscous damper was placed in the structure's side frame and middle frame, respectively. Structural design has increasingly focused on performance level, but the application of control systems like viscous dampers has received less attention. The study aims to address this gap and analyze the control system's effect on the structure's performance level. To optimize the performance level of the structure, the study used the Harris Hawks optimization algorithm (HHO) and set design restrictions to ensure that the story drift ratio is less than 2%, satisfying the life safety performance level according to FEMA-356 classification [14]. Nonlinear dynamic analysis of the structure was conducted using three different acceleration categories. The results showed that placing the viscous damper in the side spans of the frame reduced the maximum story drift by 90%, while placement in the middle spans resulted in a 70% reduction. The VD system in the P1 position was the most effective in reducing roof displacement, roof acceleration, and global drift ratio.

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Roof displacement, roof acceleration, and Global drift ratio decreased by 47.24%, 48.71%, and 56.18%, respectively, when the VD system was placed in the P1 position. Meanwhile, roof displacement, roof acceleration, and Global drift ratio in P2 mode decreased by 31.49%, 40.48%, and 46.71%, respectively.

In the present study, the location issue will be very effective in using the viscous damper. Location will significantly affect the performance of this type of system by reducing the dynamic response of the structure. Therefore, two phases have been used in this study to arrange the viscous damper in the building frame. In the first phase, the viscous damper is placed in the row of the side frame of the designed structure, and the analysis will be performed. In the second phase, the viscous damper is placed in the middle frame of the structure, and the analysis will be performed. A critical issue in structural design and analysis in recent years is the structure design based on performance level. In the process and direction of studies, less attention has been paid to the functional design of structures using control systems such as viscous dampers. In the course of studies, there will be this need and gap in studies that the level of performance that today has a significant impact on stability structure should be considered. In this study, an attempt has been made to analyze and design the structure using the mentioned control system, taking into account the issue of performance level and the effect of this type of control system (viscous damper) in reducing or increasing the performance level structure. Therefore, to consider the performance level of the structure in the optimization process, which has been used using the Harris Hawks optimization algorithm (HHO), the design restrictions have been set in such a way that the story drift ratio is less than 2% so that the performance level of life safety in Designs should be satisfied according to FEMA-356 classification [14]. It should be noted that three different classifications of acceleration have been used to perform nonlinear dynamic analysis of the structure, such that the ratio of maximum acceleration to maximum velocity is less than 0.8, 0.8 up to 1.2, and more than 1.2. Results show that the viscous damper will reduce the maximum story drift by 90% when placed in the side spans of the frame and by 70% when placed in the middle spans. The results show that the VD system in the P1 position performs best in reducing roof displacement, roof acceleration, and global drift ratio. Roof displacement, roof acceleration, and Global drift ratio will decrease by 47.24%, 48.71%, and 56.18%, respectively, where the placement of the VD system in the building frame is assumed to be P1. Meanwhile, roof displacement, roof acceleration, and Global drift ratio in P2 mode will decrease by 31.49%,

40.48%, and 46.71%, respectively.

2. Dynamics Equations of Motion

This section describes the dynamic equations of motion for the intended building frame equipped with the VD system. For this purpose, an M -bay, N -story building frame is considered. The VD system is connected to the structure with two separate phases to minimize the story drift ratio and, in general, the performance level of the structure. The nonlinear behavior of the structure is considered to calculate the story drift ratio and, in general, the performance level of the structure. The equations of motion of the multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF) system under $\ddot{x}_g(t)$ seismic acceleration are expressed as follows [15]:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{x}(t) + \mathbf{C}\dot{x}(t) + \mathbf{K}x(t) = -\mathbf{M}l\ddot{x}_g(t). \quad (1)$$

Where l is a unit vector with length $(n+1)$ and \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{K} , and x are the matrix of mass, damping, stiffness, and displacement vector, respectively. The above expressions are generally expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} m_{S,1} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_{S,2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & m_{S,i} & 0 & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & 0 & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & m_{S,n-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & m_{S,n} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} (c_{S,1} + c_{S,2}) & -c_{S,2} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -c_{S,2} & (c_{S,2} + c_{S,i}) & -c_{S,i} & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & -c_{S,i} & \ddots & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & (c_{S,i} + c_{S,n-1}) & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & 0 & c_{S,n} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} (k_{S,1} + k_{S,2}) & -k_{S,2} & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -k_{S,2} & (k_{S,2} + k_{S,i}) & -k_{S,i} & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & -k_{S,i} & \ddots & 0 & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & (k_{S,i} + k_{S,n-1}) & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & 0 & (k_{S,n} + k_T) \end{bmatrix},$$

$$x(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_i \\ x_{n-1} \\ \vdots \\ x_n \end{bmatrix}$$

In equation (2) $m_{S,i}$, $k_{S,i}$ and $c_{S,i}$, the mass, stiffness, and damping of the stories are such that $i = (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ respectively, In addition, x_i is the displacement rate of the stories such that $i = (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ respectively.

3. The system with Viscous Damper

According to the principle of fluid compression and circulation, viscous dampers can dissipate energy by applying a resisting force over a finite displacement. During seismic action, the energy generated by the imposed movement is transmitted to the damper, which forces the passage of a high-viscosity fluid through very small orifices using a cylinder-piston system (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Viscous damper components [16]

The following constitutive equation defines the viscous damper behavior:

$$F = CV^\alpha \quad (3)$$

In relation (3) F , C , V and α are Damper output force, Damping constant, Damper velocity, and Velocity exponent, respectively. In the following equation, the Damper output force is defined for modeling the spring in the viscous damper as follows:

$$F = K_d d_K = CV^\alpha \quad (4)$$

In relation (4), K_d and d_K are the series spring constant and the deformation across the spring, respectively. The Figure below shows the modeling of the viscous damper with stiffness and damping.

Figure 2. Viscous damper modeling schematic

The Figure below shows the hysteresis response of the viscous damper with the parameters suggested in reference [17, 18] to increase the sinusoidal displacement of 12, 24, and 36 mm and the frequency of 0.5 Hz. The sensitivity of the viscous damper to its speed power is shown in the Figure below for the following set of parameters.

Figure 3. Viscous Damper with variations of different input parameters [17, 18]

3.1 Story Drift Ratio

To understand the change in the relative location of the story, which is also known as story drift, one must first understand the displacement of the story. Story displacement is the deviation of a story relative to the base of the structure or the ground level. Objectively, we can expect the total displacement values of the structure as the height of the structure increases. So, the drift ratio of the story is the degree of deviation of one story compared to the story before it. Figure (4) shows the displacement of the stories.

Figure 4. Story displacement

According to the displacement of the story from the dynamic analysis of the structure, the calculation of the drift ratio of the story is straightforward. In general, to obtain the drift ratio value of the story, the displacement of the desired story is subtracted from the displacement of our previous story, and the obtained value of the story is called the drift ratio of the story. How to calculate the relative story drift ratio is described as follows:

$$\delta_1 = \frac{\Delta_1}{H_1} \quad \delta_2 = \frac{(\Delta_2 - \Delta_1)}{H_2} \quad (5)$$

In relation (5) δ_1 and δ_2 are the drift ratio of the first story and the drift ratio of the second story, respectively.

4. Performance level

FEMA-356 [14] defines different levels of performance based on the drift ratio criteria of stories (Table (1)). According to Table (1), when the drift ratio of the story is less than 1%, structural elements are partially damaged. This level of performance is called immediate occupancy (IO). In addition, when the drift ratio of stories is equal to 2%, the structural and non-structural elements are significantly damaged; this level of performance is called Life Safety (LS) mode. For the drift ratio of stories equal to 4%, the state of collapse prevention (CP) is defined, and the structure is about to collapse. Finally, for the collapsed state (C), the

drift ratio of stories is greater than 4%, and the structure is completely collapsed.

Table 1. Performance level according to FEMA-356[14] for steel moment-resisting frames

Performance level	IO	LS	CP	C
Story drift (%)	1	2	4	>4

5. Optimum design of the VD system

Since the beginning of history, the main problem of earthquakes has been the destruction and damage of structures, and the result is the death of people due to the collapse of structures. Displacement and high acceleration of the structure are two factors in the failure of structures. Nowadays, science tries to reduce the acceleration and displacement of structures by using vibration control systems, which reduce the collapse of structures. Nowadays, several methods have been developed to control the seismic response of the structure. VD control system is in the category of passive structure control systems. In this section, the optimization of VD parameters, including stiffness K_d , damping C_d , and velocity exponent α to minimize the story drift ratio under earthquake load. In general, the optimization process is described as follows:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \text{Find:} & K_d, C_d, \alpha \\
 \text{Minimize:} & DR(m_T, k_T) \\
 \text{Subjected to:} & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} K_d^{\min} \leq K_d \leq K_d^{\max} \\ C_d^{\min} \leq C_d \leq C_d^{\max} \\ \alpha^{\min} \leq \alpha \leq \alpha^{\max} \\ DR^{\text{story}^j} \leq 0.02 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \end{array} \right. \quad (6)
 \end{array}$$

In relation (6), K_d^{\min} and K_d^{\max} indicate the upper and lower bound of VD stiffness, respectively.

Also, C_d^{\min} and C_d^{\max} show the upper and lower bound of VD damping, respectively, and finally,

α^{\min} and α^{\max} show the upper and lower bound of Velocity exponent of VD, respectively. It

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also shows the amount of drift ratio in the j th story of the structure and n the number of stories. The values of the upper and lower limits of other restrictions are also considered based on references [13, 19] in the form of Tables (2).

Table 2. The bounds of optimal design variables used in the VD system [13, 18]

Parameter	$C_d (N/s/mm)$	$K_d (N/mm)$	α
Upper bound	3×10^3	10×10^2	2.00
Lower bound	10×10^{-2}	10×10^{-5}	0.01

6. Harris Hawks optimization algorithm [20]

This algorithm is inspired by the interactive and participatory behavior of a type of falcon in nature called the Harris Falcon. To hunt, these falcons form a kind of interaction and social behavior with each other to surprise and hunt the prey. With the idea of hunting Harris hawk, the Harris Hawks Optimization algorithm (HHO) has been formulated and has good power in solving optimization problems [20]. In the optimization process with the HHO algorithm, the number of search factors and the number of iterations per search factor is 30, eventually leading to a different number of cycles for optimization. The steps of the algorithm are described in the Figure below:

Figure 5. Different stages of the HHO algorithm [20]

6.1 Exploration stage

In this part, the HHO discovery mechanism is explained. If we consider the nature of Harris's hawk, this type of bird can track and identify the prey with its powerful eyes, but sometimes the prey will not be easily seen. In the following algorithm, hawks are candidate solutions, and the best candidate solution in each step is considered the desired or nearly optimal prey. In this part, the falcons randomly wait for the prey in the designated area. If we assume an equal chance q for each waiting strategy, they are sitting based on the position of the other members and the prey modeled in equation (7).

$$X(t+1) = \begin{cases} X_{rand}(t) - r_1 |X_{rand}(t) - 2r_2 X(t)| & q \geq 0.5 \\ (X_{rabbit}(t) - X_m(t)) - r_3(LB + r_4(UB - LB)) & q < 0.5 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

So in relation (7), $X(t+1)$ is the vector of the position of the hawks in the t -dimensional iteration, $X_{rabbit}(t)$ the position of the prey, $X(t)$ is the vector of the current position of the

hawks, r_1 , r_2 , r_3 , r_4 and q are random numbers in (0,1) that in each iteration LB and UB show the upper and lower bounds of the variables. $X_{rand}(t)$ is a randomly selected Harris hawk from the initial population, and X_m is the mean location. In the following equation, the relationship of average position is described.

$$X_m(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N X_i(t) \quad (8)$$

So in relation (8) $X_i(t)$ is the location of each hawk in each repetition, t and N represent the total number of hawks. It is possible to obtain the average position differently; this is the simplest rule.

6.2 The transition from exploration to exploitation

The HHO algorithm can switch from exploration to exploitation and then between different exploitation behaviors based on the escape energy of the prey. A prey's energy is significantly reduced during escape behavior. To model this fact, the energy of prey is modeled as follows:

$$E = 2E_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{T}\right) \quad (9)$$

In relation (9), E represents the escape energy of the prey, T is the maximum number of repetitions, and E_0 is the initial state of its energy.

6.3 Exploitation stage

At this stage, Harris hawks make a surprise jump by attacking the target prey identified in the previous stage. However, prey often flees from a threatening situation. Hence, different styles of pursuit occur in real situations. According to Harris's hawk's prey escape behaviors and chasing strategies, there will be four possible strategies in HHO for modeling. Available strategies include soft siege, hard siege, soft besiege with progressive rapid dives, and hard besiege with progressive rapid dives. In this section, due to the wide range of these strategies, only the names of these strategies are mentioned, and for a complete and comprehensive view of this strategy, refer to reference [20].

7. 6-story moment-resisting steel frame

The OpenSees software is employed to conduct a dynamic analysis of a 2D steel frame building. The frame is equipped with a Viscous Damper (VD) and modeled using two approaches - distributed and concentrated plasticity. Wong [21] has studied the behavior of the VD in the frame using the concentrated plasticity approach, which is more suitable for modeling the large-scale nonlinear behavior of steel moment-resisting frames [22]. Although considering the P-M interaction, the distributed plasticity model is complicated to model numerically due to localized effects like local buckling. Using a concentrated plasticity model requires defining the nonlinear behavior of the panel zone for each steel frame element.

Figure 6. 6-story frame modeling with connecting spring

In modeling this structure, a centralized plasticity model is performed in OpenSees software, and at the junction of the beam to the column, a nonlinear spring with zero length is attached to

the element, representing the centralized plasticity model (see Figure 6). In modeling beams and columns, elastic materials have been used, and in this section, to simulate the behavior of two-line hysteresis of springs, the Modified Ibarra-Medina-Krawinkler (IMK) model has been used; the behavior of this model can be seen in Figures (7 and 8). In modeling the mentioned bending frame, to model the three-dimensional behavior of the structure in the two-dimensional plane, the elements of the leaning columns are used to apply this function well in the structure. It should be noted that the leaning columns will not affect the structure's main behavior and are intended only for using three-dimensional plan loads on a two-dimensional plane.

Figure 7. (a) View of the connection spring (b) How to model the spring in the connection spring [23]

Figure 8. The hysteresis curve for the modified IMK behavioral decline model [24]

In this study, two different processes have been assumed to place the viscous damper. In the Figure below, the design and analysis process of the controlled structure is described along with the viscous damper.

Figure 9. The different processes of locating the viscous damper

8. Dynamic analysis

This article uses the records of Landers, Loma Prieta, and Chi-Chi earthquakes for nonlinear dynamic analysis of the structure. Table (3) shows the earthquake records used in

this article.

Table 3. Parameters of studied earthquakes

Type	Earthquake	PGA (m/sec ²)	PGA/PGV (g.sec/m)	Strong ground motion duration (sec)	Predominant Period (sec)	Total time duration (sec)	Arias Intensity (m/sec)
	Chi Chi	9.81	0.52	30.385	0.16	89.995	20.105
Near	Landers	9.81	1.027	10.577	0.32	27.998	15.22
	Loma Prieta	9.81	1.344	12.15	0.28	39.99	16.863

9. Results

This section analyzes the structure under the Landers, Loma Prieta, and Chi-Chi earthquakes. The optimal values for the viscous damper have been calculated using the HHO optimization algorithm. Table (4) shows the optimal values of VD system parameters. Table (5) also shows the first three natural periods of uncontrolled and controlled structures with two separate processes.

Table 4. Optimum parameters for VD system subjected to earthquakes

System	System placement	Schematic	K_d	C_d	α
VD	P1		523.14	1483.83	1.00
	P2		566.11	1513.78	1.33

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Table 5. The first three natural periods of the studied structures

System	System placement	T_1	T_2	T_3
Uncontrol	-	1.2424	0.4465	0.2541
Controlled by VD	P1	1.6151	0.5785	0.3292
	P2	1.4772	0.5021	0.2860

According to Table (5), using the first process (P1) for placing the system in the building frame and controlling it with the VD system is expected to result in a more significant increase in the structure's three natural periods compared to the second process (P2). On average, the increase in the three natural periods in P1 mode is 29%, while in P2 mode, the growth is expected to be 14% on average. Table (6) also displays the reduction of roof displacement, roof acceleration, and global drift ratio in the uncontrolled and controlled state using the VD system in two cases, P1 and P2. Based on the numerical findings in Tables (5 and 6), it can be concluded that the VD system, which is optimized with the HHO algorithm in P1 and P2 mode, can effectively lessen the roof's displacement and acceleration and the structure drift.

Table 6. A comparison between the responses of the controlled and uncontrolled structures subjected to earthquakes

System	System placement	Roof disp. (m)	Roof accel. (g)	Global drift ratio	Reduction Percentage (%)		
					Roof disp.	Roof accel.	Global drift ratio
Uncontrol	-	1.8122	1.7214	0.0897			
Controlled by VD	P1	0.9561	0.8829	0.0393	47.24	48.71	56.18
	P2	1.2414	1.0245	0.0478	31.49	40.48	46.71

The results indicate that the VD system performs better in P1 mode, reducing roof displacement, acceleration, and global drift ratio. With the VD system placed in the building frame at P1, roof displacement, roof acceleration, and global drift ratio have decreased by

47.24%, 48.71%, and 56.18%, respectively. On the other hand, when the VD system was placed in P2 mode, roof displacement, roof acceleration, and global drift ratio decreased by 31.49%, 40.48%, and 46.71%, respectively. Based on the numerical results presented in the Table, it can be concluded that the VD system, when optimally arranged in the P1 mode, significantly reduces roof displacement, roof acceleration, and global drift ratio. Such a reduction in these parameters is essential in ensuring stability and continued activity of the structure after applying dynamic loads such as those caused by earthquakes. Figures (10 and 11) display the maximum values of story drift in both controlled and uncontrolled structures in P1 and P2 modes.

Figure 10. The maximum drift ratio of the controlled and uncontrolled structure subjected to earthquakes (P1)

The data presented in Figure (10) illustrates that the VD system has significantly reduced the maximum values of story drift in the controlled structure with optimal parameters. The results show that the VD system placed in P1 mode has reduced the maximum values of Story drift by 90%. According to Table (1), the maximum value of story drift in the

uncontrolled structure is more than 4%, which means the structure is likely to collapse (C). However, the maximum values of story drift in the controlled structure in P1 mode are close to 2%, which means that the structure is considered to be in life safety mode (LS). Additionally, Figure (10) shows that the VD system not only reduces the maximum values of Story drift but also improves the performance level of the structure, which is a crucial factor in designing essential structures. Furthermore, based on the results presented in Figure (10), it can be concluded that the VD system in P1 mode has distributed the range of maximum values of story drift more uniformly throughout the height of the controlled structure, which can further reduce the maximum value of Story drift and improve the overall performance level of the structure. Finally, Figure (11) displays the maximum values of Story drift in uncontrolled and controlled structures with a VD system in P2 mode.

Figure 11. The maximum drift ratio of the controlled and uncontrolled structure subjected to earthquakes (P2)

The results depicted in Figure (11) indicate that the VD system has effectively decreased the maximum values of story drift in the controlled case with optimal parameters. Specifically,

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the structure controlled by VD in the P2 mode showed a remarkable reduction of 70% in the maximum values of Story drift. According to the performance level mentioned in Table (1), the maximum value of story drift in the uncontrolled structure is over 4%, implying that the structure might collapse (C). However, the maximum values of story drift in the controlled structure in P2 mode are nearly 2%, which, according to Table (1), puts the structure in life safety mode (LS). The VD system not only reduces the maximum values of Story drift but also improves the performance level of the structure, as evident from Figure (11). Additionally, the results suggest that the VD system in P2 mode has evenly distributed the range of maximum values of story drift in the controlled structure's height, which can further lower the maximum values of Story drift and enhance the structure's performance level. In conclusion, the results indicate that the VD system's performance in P2 mode is more appropriate than in P1 mode in reducing the maximum values of story drift, roof displacement, roof acceleration, and global drift ratio.

10. Conclusion

This study examined the effectiveness of the viscous damper system in reducing roof displacement, roof acceleration, global drift ratio, and maximum values of Story drift by evaluating two different positioning modes. The experiment was conducted on a building frame under earthquake excitation with three categories. The HHO algorithm was utilized to obtain the optimal values of the viscous damper system, which were then used to minimize the maximum values of story drift. The results suggest that the VD system placed in position P1 (side frames of the structure) performs better in reducing roof displacement, acceleration, global drift ratio, and maximum story drift values than the P2 mode (middle spans of the structure). It was also observed that both positioning modes of the VD system could increase the structure's performance level by reducing the maximum values of story drift, thus improving the performance level from the collapsed state (C) to the life safety state (LS). This finding is significant from the structural and earthquake engineering perspective as it contributes to designing structures with optimal performance levels.

11. Acknowledgments

The authors thank the Vocational Boy's College of Shahrekord for their spiritual support.

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12. Funding

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

13. Conflict of Interests

The authors confirm that there is no conflict of interest.

14. Availability of Data and Materials

The datasets used and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

15. Competing Interests

The authors confirm that there is no conflict of interest.

16. Authors' Contributions

Mohammad Alibabaei Shahraki: Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Amirhossein Hosseini Chaleshtori:** Investigation, Methodology, Conceptualization

17. Reference

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